

Evaluation of the Management of Femur Fracture in Children Under 6 Years

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Abstract:

Introduction: Pediatric femoral shaft fractures are more commonly seen in children of age 1-6 years. Different treatment approaches are used based on the age, fracture characteristics, and preferences of the surgeon. Previously Spica casting was the primarily used treatment option but other treatment options like intramedullary nailing and plate osteosynthesis have become common in recent years.

Aim and Objective: To evaluate the demographics and treatment trends in pediatric femoral shaft fractures in children aged 1-6 years.

Methods: Data was collected from 87 patients with femoral shaft fractures in children with age 1-6 years retrospectively. Demographic data like age, sex, ethnicity, and treatment modalities were analyzed. Treatment options like Spica casting, intramedullary nail, plate osteosynthesis, brace, splinting, external fixation and others were included. The statistical was performed using ANOVA, chi-square test, and t-test.

Results: Spica casting was the most often used treatment (71.2%), and the majority of patients were males (77%), were between the ages of 1-3 years (72.4%). By age group, however, treatment trends differed considerably. While older children (ages 4-6) were more likely to receive intramedullary nails (37.5%) or plate osteosynthesis (25%), spica casting was more common in younger children (92% in ages 1-3). Spica casting has been less common over time, but intramedullary nails and plate osteosynthesis have become more common from 2016 to 2020.

Conclusion: Patients aged 1-3 years are more likely to receive non-surgical methods like spica casting, whereas children aged 4-6 years are more likely to have surgical procedures like plate osteosynthesis and intramedullary nails.

Keywords: Femur, Pediatric Femoral Shaft Fractures, Spica Casting, Intramedullary Nail, Plate Osteosynthesis.

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Introduction

In children, femoral shaft fracture involving lower limbs is the most common to be observed [1,2]. In Europe, every year at least 20/100000 cases occur in infants [3]. The femur is the strongest and largest bone that needs specialized care when fractured due to several persistent complications like growth deformities. Fractures are categorized into stable (minimum displacement of broken ends of bones) and unstable fractures (spiral or oblique fractures) by the American Academy of Orthopedic Surgeons (AAOS) [4]. The reason for such injury could be high-energy trauma for instance vehicle crashes, falls, high-impact sports injury, and low-energy trauma including pathological fractures like cerebral palsy [5].

A proximal and distal physis make up a basic developmental segment between the epiphysis and metaphysis of the pediatric femur. Consequently, intramedullary devices must be placed correctly to not disrupt these development plates [6]. Until the time of physeal fusion, arterial supply to the femoral head is mainly in the form of the deep branch of the medial femoral circumflex artery. Damage to the arterial branches may also cause avascular necrosis of the femoral head because they lie in proximity to possible intramedullary nail puncture sites [7].

The pediatric femur is very different from the adult, changing from weak woven bone to stronger

lamellar bone throughout childhood. This means it can tolerate more deformity in terms of angulation and shortening compared with the older child but cannot as well tolerate torsional deformities [8]. Because cortical thickness, area moment of inertia, and geometry increase across age groups, children's bone strength does increase with age, making them more likely to suffer high-energy trauma-related teenage fractures [9].

In infants, non-accidental fractures are mostly seen specifically at the age before they learn walking mostly due to long bone fractures as a result of abuse [10,11]. Pavlik harness, traction, and spica casting are non-surgical treatments used to treat diaphyseal fractures in children [12] whereas submuscular plating, elastic nails, rigid nails, as well as internal and external fixation are opted for when surgeries are in demand [13].

Initially, the physical examinations of the femoral fracture show tender and swelling in the site of injury [3] and Waddell's triad (ipsilateral femoral shaft fracture, ipsilateral intra-thoracic or intra-abdominal injury and contralateral head injury) are observed in road accidents [14]. Radiological images can be promising in conformational diagnosis of fracture [3]. Pathological fractures can be prevented if babies carefully with hip flexion contractures [15]. Child abuse mostly results in skeletal injury. The femur injury is considered the second most common cause of such injury first being the humerus [15].

To manage fractures the age of the patients is the major factor to be considered along with weight, type of fracture and whether polytrauma is present [2]. In comparison with the non-surgical techniques, surgical methods are typically applied to fix fractures in older children because of short-term hospital stays, fewer complications and early mobility [2,16]. Non-surgical techniques are beneficial in the case of children less than 6 years old because of exclusive bone remodelling and speedy repair with fewer complications [17].

This evaluative study aims to better understand various approaches to managing femoral fractures in children under 6 years of age that focus on the effectiveness of surgical and non-surgical techniques. By analyzing clinical evidence, the study provides specific insights into the unique treatment requirement in pediatric cases.

Methods

Study Design: This is a retrospective study whose data was obtained from a Medical College in India. The study was conducted from November 2023 to April 2024. 87 patients in the age group of 1-6 years participated in the study. The demographic data of the patients were collected from the college hospital. This study included patients aged 1-6

years with the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) diagnosis codes with femoral shaft fracture and a corresponding ICD-10 procedure code. Demographic data like age, sex, race, and ethnicity were collected from the patient. Spica casting, Intramedullary nails, Brace, Splint, External fixation, and Plate osteosynthesis are the types of treatment used for patients in treating Femur shaft fractures. The study utilized graphs to evaluate trends in the use of different treatment modalities for pediatric femoral fractures, including spica casting, intramedullary nails, and plate osteosynthesis. Stratified by age groups, Figure 1 illustrated overall trends for patients aged 1-6 years, and Figure 2 focused on those aged 1-3 years and 4-6 years, visually representing the changes in treatment frequency over time. These graphs facilitated the identification of significant trends, such as the decrease in spica casting and increased use of intramedullary nails and plate osteosynthesis and allowed for easy comparison of management strategies between different age groups, highlighting that spica casting was more common in younger patients, while older children increasingly received intramedullary nails and plate osteosynthesis.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Patients having femoral shaft fractures in the age group of 1-6 years were included in the study and those who are willing to participate and provide informed consent are included in the study. Patients who do not provide informed consent and are not willing to participate in the study are excluded from the study.

Statistical Analysis: Data entry and statistical analysis were done using ANOVA statistical software. The proper percentage comparisons between the various groups were made using the mean values, standard deviations, student's t-test, and Chi-square. Significant data was defined as a P value of 0.05.

Results

Table 1 presents demographic data and treatment modalities for pediatric femoral shaft fractures among 87 patients. The mean age of the patients is 3.1 years, with a standard deviation of 1.7 years. The majority of the patients, 72.4% (63 patients), are aged between 1 to 3 years, while 27.6% (24 patients) are between 4 to 6 years. The sample predominantly consists of male patients, who account for 77% (67 patients), while females represent 22.9% (20 patients). Regarding treatment methods, spica casting is the most commonly used technique, applied in 71.2% of the cases (62 patients). Intramedullary nailing is used in 13.7% (12 patients), while plate osteosynthesis is performed in 9.1% (8 patients). Other treatment options, including splint, brace, and external

fixation, are each used in 1.1% (1 patient) of the cases, and 2.2% (2 patients) received alternative

forms of treatment.

Table 1: Demographic data and management of pediatric femoral shaft fractures of the patients

Demographic	n (%) (N=87)
Age years (mean, SD)	3.1 (1.7)
Age	
1-3 years	63 (72.4%)
4-6 years	24 (27.6%)
Sex	
Male	67 (77%)
Female	20 (22.9%)
Treatment (%)	
Intramedullary nail	12 (13.7%)
Spica casting	62 (71.2%)
Splint	1 (1.1%)
Plate Osteosynthesis	8 (9.1%)
Brace	1 (1.1%)
External fixation	1 (1.1%)
Other	2 (2.2%)

Table 2 compares demographic characteristics and treatment methods between two age groups: 1-3 years and 4-6 years. Out of the 87 patients, 63 are aged 1-3 years, and 24 are aged 4-6 years. A statistically significant difference in sex distribution exists between the two groups ($p = 0.04$), with 74.6% males in the younger age group and 70.8% in the older age group. In terms of ethnicity, 19% of the younger group and 16.7% of the older group are Hispanic, while non-Hispanic children comprise 80.9% and 83.3% of these

groups, respectively ($p = 0.4$). Significant differences in treatment methods are observed ($p < 0.01$). In the 1-3 year group, spica casting is the predominant treatment (92%), whereas in the 4-6 year group, intramedullary nailing is more common (37.5%). Plate osteosynthesis is used more frequently in the older group (25%) compared to the younger group (3.17%). Other treatment methods show minimal variation across the age groups.

Table 2: Differences in demographic and management of pediatric shaft fractures by age

Demographic	Age 1-3 years	Age 4-6 years	P value
N	63	24	
Sex			0.04
Male	47 (74.6%)	17 (70.8%)	
Female	16 (25.3%)	7 (29.2%)	
Treatment (%)			<0.01
Intramedullary nail	2 (3.2%)	9 (37.5%)	
Spica casting	58 (92%)	7 (29.2%)	
Splint	1 (1.6%)	1 (4.1)	
Plate Osteosynthesis	2 (3.17%)	6 (25%)	
Brace	0	0	
External fixation	0	0	
Other	1 (1.6%)	1 (4.1)	

Table 3 shows the differences in demographic characteristics and management of pediatric femoral shaft fractures by sex. Among the 87 patients, 67 are male, and 20 are female. Age distribution differs significantly between the sexes ($p = 0.011$); 71.6% of male patients are aged 1-3 years compared to 65% of female patients, while 28.4% of males are in the 4-6 year age group compared to 35% of females. Ethnicity does not show a statistically significant difference between males and females ($p = 0.6$), with Hispanics

comprising 17.9% of the male group and 15% of the female group. Regarding treatment methods, there are significant differences ($p < 0.01$). Spica casting is used more frequently in males (74.6%) than in females (58.3%), while intramedullary nailing is used similarly in both sexes (11.9% in males and 12.5% in females). The use of plate osteosynthesis is also comparable between males (8.9%) and females (8.3%), and the application of a brace shows little difference (4.5% in males versus 5% in females).

Table 3: Differences in demographic and management of pediatric shaft fractures by sex

Demographic	Male	Female	p-value
N	67	20	
Age group			0.011
1-3 years	48 (71.6%)	13 (65%)	
4-6 years	19 (28.4%)	7 (35%)	
Ethnicity (%)			0.6
Hispanic	12 (17.9%)	3 (15%)	
Non-Hispanic	55 (82%)	17 (85%)	
Treatment (%)			<0.01
Intramedullary nail	8 (11.9%)	3 (12.5%)	
Spica casting	50 (74.6%)	14 (58.3%)	
Plate Osteosynthesis	6 (8.9%)	2 (8.3%)	
Brace	3 (4.5%)	1 (5%)	

Discussion

Neonatal femoral injuries during birth are extremely uncommon and only occur in less than 1% of cases [18] where there are breech births and complicated deliveries [19]. Almost 60% of childhood cases are found to be happened because of confirmed child abuse. In this case multifaceted management approach should take into account that possess involvement of social activists and child protection services considering the socioeconomic and behavioural patterns of victims [20].

A simple splint is usually instituted immediately to stabilize and reduce the pain in infants with femoral diaphyseal fractures. This is followed by instituting a Pavlik harness to stabilize the fractured femur and maintain the best possible reduction for the femur [21]. To manage the femoral shaft fractures in neonates, immobilization with a Pavlik harness is a wonderful standard [22], as this allows rapid callus formation with few complications [23].

There are several disadvantages of the Pavlik harness. It is very troublesome to apply and adjust. Prolonged hospital stays are a direct result, as well as being expensive, and difficult nursing care with frequent diaper changes is required [22]. Infants in this age have excellent remodelling capabilities for angulation and length difference between the limbs, till 15 mm of shortening and 30 degrees of angulation possible [24]. When a Pavlik harness is used on an infant, results show greater acceptance of malunion, malalignment, and shortening. Hip spica casting is a good option when dealing with extremely infrequent unhinged fractures where a Pavlik harness cannot provide enough support; yet some complications may arise, such as skin ulcerations and malalignment. Traction does not usually need to be applied to cases of femoral fracture at this age [22].

However, in unstable, comminuted fractures with more than 2 centimetres of preliminary shortening, that is not well managed with early spica casting (within 48 hours from the time of injury), this

management is still possible [25]. If traction is necessary, the kind of traction that is utilized usually corresponds to the child's size. Hamilton-Russell skin tractions are frequently used for infants with ≥ 12 kg to improve relief and stability, while gallews traction is usually the preferred method of skin traction for younger children (< 12 kg) [8]. The older the child, the longer he needs to stay immobilized. Operative techniques then become preferable because of earlier mobilization, lesser hospital costs, and much lesser social impacts on the family involved [26].

External fixation remains the immediate treatment choice for emergencies with unstable open fractures or multiple injuries. This enables stabilization of the fracture within a half hour, which allows life-saving measures to continue [27]. It has some complications, such as pin-tract infections. However, it provides a means to establish early stability. Definitive internal fixation reduces the risks of late complications and enhances the healing of the fractures [28].

Complications of femoral fractures in children include malunion, limb length discrepancy, and psychological effects resulting from immobilization [29]. Overgrowth of the femur after fracture may lead to limb length discrepancy, which normally spontaneously corrects. Malalignment does sometimes require surgical correction for deformities if remodelling is not adequate. Delayed immobilization causes frustration and immobilization, loss of active mobility for the child, social isolation, and anxiety in parents; follow-up psychosocial support calls for the utilization of child-supportive care [30].

To conclude, the management of femoral fractures in children less than 6 years is extremely successful with high healing rates and very good long-term results. Most methods of non-surgical treatment are well-adapted and effective, but surgical methods are normally applied in cases where there is a need for early mobilization. Decisions should therefore

depend individually upon the needs of the child and the characteristics of the fracture. The healing process, functional recovery, and quality of life will be best balanced in conjunction with psychosocial support.

Conclusion

The study has concluded that the management of pediatric femoral shaft fractures is significantly influenced by both age and sex. Younger patients (1-3 years) are predominantly treated with spica casting, while older patients (4-6 years) are more likely to undergo surgical interventions such as intramedullary nailing and plate osteosynthesis. Male patients, who constitute the majority of cases, are more frequently treated with spica casting compared to females. These findings suggest that treatment approaches should be carefully considered based on demographic factors to optimize outcomes in pediatric femoral shaft fractures. The findings from the analysis of pediatric femoral shaft fractures among 87 patients provide significant insights into demographic patterns and treatment modalities. The majority of patients are male (77%), with a mean age of 3.1 years, and the most common treatment method is spica casting (71.2%). Age plays a crucial role in the choice of treatment, with spica casting predominantly used in younger patients (1-3 years), whereas older patients (4-6 years) are more likely to receive intramedullary nailing or plate osteosynthesis, as demonstrated by statistically significant differences in treatment methods ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, a notable gender disparity is evident, with males more frequently undergoing spica casting compared to females (74.6% vs. 58.3%, $p < 0.01$). Ethnicity shows no significant impact on treatment choices across age or gender groups. Overall, this study highlights the influence of both age and sex on the management of pediatric femoral shaft fractures, suggesting tailored approaches to treatment based on demographic factors.

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